

Patterns of Algiarism and Plagiarism in Sci-Tech Communication: Implications for Academic Integrity

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Abstract: Academic integrity promotes the principles of honesty, trust, fairness, respect and responsibility in scholarship, but is increasingly challenged by both traditional forms of plagiarism and evolving forms such as AI-giarism or AI-assisted plagiarism. A corpus of 37 scientific papers was examined using Turnitin, with the aim of identifying the patterns of plagiarism and AI usage. From the findings, the commonest forms of plagiarism practiced were mosaic, verbatim plagiarism and omission of quotations. Plagiarism occurred mostly across sections of the paper and in the introduction and literature review sections. The same pattern was observed with regard to AI-generated content in the sections. An inverse relationship was observed between AI-generated papers and the papers with high similarity indexes. It was concluded that AI has become a tool to reduce incidences of plagiarism, and that plagiarism and Algiarism practices are mostly deliberate. Also, there is the need to identify the blurred line between the use of AI as an assistive tool, and its misuse as a primary knowledge creator. Recommendations suggested include targeted academic training on ethical writing practices, and a re-engineering of existing plagiarism detection tools and methods, to better capture subtle and evolving forms of academic misconduct.

Keywords: *Academic integrity, Algiarism, Plagiarism, Academic misconduct, Generative AI*

INTRODUCTION

Research on academic integrity has become common in studies in scholarship and higher education since the evolution of AI. Five core values identified by The International Center for Academic Integrity are honesty, trust, fairness, respect, and responsibility, and the courage to uphold them, even under pressure (Fishman, 2014). These principles are essential in encouraging a culture of ethical research, teaching, and learning. The rapid adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) tools such as ChatGPT, Claude and Grok, is a major driver of these new challenges to academic integrity.

Plagiarism is traditionally understood as the presentation of other people's ideas, words, or creations as one's own. The American Psychological Association (2025) identifies plagiarism, whether intentional or unintentional, as a serious violation of ethical standards that denies rightful credit to original authors. With the rise of generative AI, a new form of misconduct has emerged, referred to as Algiarism, a type of plagiarism facilitated by AI tools (Waqas, Hania, & Chunyan, 2025). This type of misconduct often enables users to generate entire documents or solutions with minimal effort, thus blurring the line between support and substitution. Tools like ChatGPT and other generative AI can be used ethically to support the teaching and learning process, as well as research, but their potential for misuse has raised critical concerns for academic communities globally.

The consequences of plagiarism are extensive and destructive to academia. Plagiarism not only compromises personal integrity, but also erodes trust within academic and professional communities. Repercussions could be academic, including failing grades, suspension, or expulsion; professional, such as job loss and reputational harm; legal, including lawsuits and penalties for copyright infringement; and psychological, with long-term effects on self-esteem and professional

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relationships (Ashikuzzaman, 2024). Many institutions take plagiarism so seriously that they have designed formal educational or training programmes for students and staff on the consequences of the practice. In many institutions also, there are established policies to check AI misuse and plagiarism.

As indicated by Jereb et al. (2018), the major drivers of plagiarism among some Slovene and German university students were mainly the ease of access and use of new technologies and the Internet, which make information readily available and tempt students to bypass academic integrity norms. The study points to other factors that cause students to carry out plagiarism including academic pressure, pride, low academic motivation, lack of academic skills, and unclear teaching or methodological guidance.

The motivations for the uptake of AI tools in academia as reported by Bin-Nashwan, Sadallah and Bouteraa (2023) are the time-saving benefits, electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM), and individual factors such as academic self-esteem and self-efficacy. Also, perceived stress was identified as a motivator because academics reported turning to AI tools to reduce anxiety and meet tight deadlines. Social influence or peer pressure was found to have a negative impact on ChatGPT use as well. This may be due to ethical concerns. The study points out that while ChatGPT may provide practical benefits, its use remains a contested issue, defined by individual values and institutional expectations.

This study examines instances of plagiarism and AIgiarism based on a corpus of research papers submitted to a scientific conference organised by a professional society in Nigeria. The study aims to identify the implications of AI use and plagiarism on research integrity among scientists.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Plagiarism and AIgiarism (AI-assisted plagiarism) are forms of academic dishonesty, differentiated mainly by the source and method of content generation. Traditional plagiarism involves the unauthorised use of content from books, articles, or other students' work, without proper acknowledgment. On the other hand, AIgiarism is the use of artificial intelligence tools such as generative AI to produce content that is then submitted as original work, without disclosing the use of AI or properly attributing its contribution. Cambiara and Pyrrho (2025) hint that the misuse of AI for scholarly work has raised similar concerns as the practice of plagiarism.

Artificial intelligence has great potential in academics and administrative work due to its capacity to analyse large datasets with speed and precision (Agbor, Duke, Obaji-Akpet, Nwagboso, Eja, Awubi & Ukume, 2024). It is used at various stages of research such as literature search, outlining, brainstorming, grammar and spell checking and more recently, even peer reviewing (Wang, Bhandary, Wang & Moore, 2024).

However, Mogavi et al. (2024) point out that though viewed as a helpful tool, its capacity to water down scholarship and affect critical thinking is recognised and considered with apprehension. Another perspective on the negative side of the use of AI for research was also expressed by Agbor et al. (2024) as reduction in creativity and critical thinking, scholarly rigour; and the risks of copyright ambiguity and algorithmic bias introduced through the type of data used in training AI

models. AI models have been blamed for promoting academic indolence. For learners, it creates a lack of authentic learning (Williams, 2024).

Another challenge observed in using AI to assist scholarship is the risk of AI hallucination (Williams, 2024). This occurs if and when false or misleading information is presented as fact, for instance, fake references generated when AI is prompted to generate research material with citation/references. This has been recognised as a significant barrier to the adoption of AI in scholarly work. This is a great problem in reviewing studies because some of the false data generated, especially as fabricated references and factual distortions are difficult to detect without manual verification. Verifying such data can be time-consuming and distracting, and poses a real threat to academic integrity and trust in AI systems.

Recently, artificial intelligence is being also applied to peer review. As poignantly explained by Tang (2023), "...We could be facing a dreaded scenario in which scholarly papers are written by AI, reviewed by AI and read by AI." Wang, Bhandary, Wang and Moore (2024) reported their evaluation of the use of ChatGPT (GPT4) as a research tool in clinical and academic writing. While the tool excelled in summarizing, it was not quite effective in aspects such as citation and referencing, sourcing papers, extracting structured data from scientific tables, creating and designing diagrams, managing large quantities of text, noise sensitivity and hallucinations. Also a plagiarism risk was observed.

While AI is known to affect academic integrity, studies also show that academic integrity plays a moderating role in the relationship between AI use and its perceived benefits. Higher levels of academic integrity were shown to reduce the influence of time-saving motives and peer pressure, while enhancing the relationship between AI use and positive outcomes such as stress relief and improved academic self-concept when used ethically (Bin-Nashwan et al., 2023). These findings indicate that integrity does not merely constrain AI adoption; it also guides towards its responsible use.

Fu, Silalahi, Shih, Phuong, Eunike and Jargalsaikhan (2024) conducted a study on the level of user satisfaction with the quality of information generated through artificial intelligence among Indonesian researchers. The findings of the study show that usability, accessibility and comprehensiveness counted more to the academics/researchers than correctness, accuracy and reliability. The implications of this are not good for scholarship. Meanwhile, López Santos, Lozano and Blanco Fontao (2025) revealed from a sample of 379 teachers in Spain, that specialisation and age among other demographic factors, affected how ChatGPT was received.

Plagiarism in its purest form occurs when the original creator of knowledge is not acknowledged. Some common forms of plagiarism, as recognised by Selemani, Chawmga and Dube (2018) in their study of Mzuzu University postgraduate students, were paraphrasing without acknowledgment (most common) summarizing without acknowledgment, using quotation marks, incorrect or lack of proper citations, copy and paste, submission of another person's work as one's effort, patch writing, presenting secondary sources as primary sources and fabricating references.

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According to a study of first-year students at a university in Portugal, the most common form of plagiarism is copying materials without quotation marks and patch writing (Festas, Seixas & Matos, 2022). Zhou, Qiu, Liang and Acuna (2025) reported that paraphrased plagiarism is the most common, yet most subtle of the types of plagiarism practised among researchers. This type of plagiarism is described as subtle because generative AI tools are used to manipulate (paraphrase) text, which is not easy to detect by plagiarism detection tools since the tools are not familiar with such typologies of paraphrasing. They recommend the development of more effective tools which depend on deep learning models rather than the traditional approaches. This is because traditional approaches are only effective for simple paraphrasing typologies.

Plagiarism is described as an academic literacy issue by Matos, Seixas & Festas (2022). The findings of Sanni-Aibire, Steesz, Gerias and Vogt (2021) show that international students experience knowledge gaps about some types of plagiarism, particularly self-plagiarism and contract cheating, which constitutes outsourcing academic work. However, this lack of awareness has nothing to do with the notion that there is somehow a lack of consensus concerning the definition(s) of plagiarism. Plagiarism has a variety of meanings depending on location/institution (Rumanovska, Laziková, Taká & Stoličná, 2024). Some common variations in plagiarism that may require clarity in defining them are defective attribution, misleading representation, unintentional plagiarism, false paraphrasing, duplicate submissions across courses or platforms, representing joint efforts as individuals, and AI-generated work (Rumanovska, Laziková, Taká & Stoličná, 2024). They further noted that regulations are guided merely by ethical considerations or norms rather than legal instruments.

Studies like Selemeni, Chawmga, and Dube (2018) have attributed laziness, poor time management, and poor writing skills as the major reasons why postgraduate students fall prey to plagiarism. Also, supervisors' lack of effort in attempting to detect or reckon with plagiarised work has enabled the negative trend of plagiarism among students. The causes were thereafter classified broadly as student factors, faculty attitude, system factors (such as lack of or weak enforcement) and environmental factors (copy and paste syndrome – ease of using digital resources). In another study, Atmini et al. (2024) used the Fraud Diamond framework to show that academic pressure, rationalization (feeling of justification) and AI competency were the major factors behind plagiarism among postgraduate business students in Indonesia and Malaysia. However, opportunity was a less significant factor for indulging in plagiarism.

Faba-Pérez and Pérez-Pulido (2024), in a study involving students and staff of the Faculty of Documentation and Communication Sciences of the University of Extremadura on the level of knowledge and awareness about plagiarism, found that the masters students were found to be the highest on their knowledge of plagiarism with a mean score of 2.27 /3. The mean scores of the PhD students and bachelors students were far lower, ranging from 1.65 - 1.74. Faculty had a moderate rating of 1.95/3, while the average mean of the entire sample was 1.83. This distribution of scores point to an overwhelming lack of awareness, especially with the PhD students, whose main preoccupation is research.

Increase in access to open digital resources (Mireku, Dzamesi & Bervell, 2024) and artificial intelligence tools, especially generative AI, has increased the propensity for both plagiarism and

AIgiarism. This has also become a major challenge to academic integrity and the growth of credible science and scholarship. Based on the factors, causes, and drivers identified in previous studies explored, there is a need for a multi-pronged approach in checking the negative trends for the ultimate good of scholarship. The objective of this study is therefore to examine the nature and types of plagiarism and AIgiarism found in papers submitted to a 2025 scientific conference in Nigeria, with the aim of recommending solutions to such unethical academic practices.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What are the common types of plagiarism observed in the corpus of papers found in scientific papers submitted to the 2025 conference?
- ii. Which sections of research papers are most frequently affected by plagiarism?
- iii. Which sections of research papers are most frequently affected by AI-generation?
- iv. What are the remedies of or suggestions for reducing the negative trends?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in similarity scores among papers from different scientific disciplines.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in AI-generated content scores across academic disciplines.

H₀₃: There is no significant correlation between similarity scores and AI-generated content scores in the submitted papers.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The main objective of this study was to examine the nature (types) of plagiarism and misuse of AI-assisted writing, or “AIgiarism” among researchers who submitted their papers to a scientific conference organised by a professional society in Nigeria in 2025. The study adopted a descriptive quantitative research design. Possible disciplinary differences in the use and misuse of text-generating technologies were also investigated to determine whether a significant relationship exists between traditional similarity scores and AI-generated content detection scores.

Population and Sample

The population for this study comprised all the 156 full-length research papers submitted for consideration to the scientific conference, which was held in May 2025. The conference, which attracted participants from various scientific disciplines, represented a worthwhile opportunity to evaluate scholarly writing practices within the Nigerian scientific research context.

A purposive sampling technique was adopted, based on the inclusion criteria. Out of 156 papers submitted in their raw, unedited or reviewed form, only 37 papers covering several scientific disciplines were selected. The final sample included 37 full papers in Material Science and Engineering, Computing, Nutrition, Health Sciences, Biochemistry and Chemistry, Biotechnology and Microbiology, Agriculture, and Environmental sciences. All papers selected were full-text, based on a science or technology field and organised or formatted using the IMRD (Introduction, Methodology, Result and Discussion) or a similar arrangement.

Instrumentation

The Turnitin plagiarism tool was used to derive the Similarity Index (SI) of the selected papers. This index represents the proportion of text that matched previously published or submitted sources. It is expressed as a percentage, and is a quantitative measure of potential plagiarism. The software also provides details on matched sources to indicate verbatim and closely paraphrased content. Turnitin was also used to determine AI-generated content indicating the likelihood that parts of the submission were generated by an artificial intelligence language model. The score provides a probabilistic assessment of machine-generated content across different sections of the paper as a percentage. This index serves as a quantitative measure of potential AI-giarism.

Coding Template

A structured coding template was developed to systematically extract relevant information from each paper. The coding scheme included the following variables:

- i. Author's academic discipline
- ii. Similarity Index (percentage)
- iii. AI Score (percentage)
- iv. Sections of the paper affected (e.g., abstract, introduction, methodology, results, discussion, references)
- v. Type(s) of plagiarism (e.g., verbatim copying, mosaic plagiarism, self-plagiarism)

Procedure for Data Collection

Oral ethical approval was received from the conference organizers to access submitted manuscripts for academic research purposes. All papers were retrieved in digital format (.docx), anonymised, and prepared for analysis. Each paper was first uploaded to the Turnitin software to obtain similarity reports and the AI reports. The results were recorded using the coding template. The sample of 37 papers was independently reviewed by a research assistant to establish inter-rater reliability. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion and consensus.

Method of Data Analysis

Data obtained from the plagiarism and AI detection tools were entered into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 27 for analysis. The following statistical procedures were employed:

- i. Descriptive statistics, including frequency distributions, the number of plagiarised documents, documents with significant AI content and observed patterns.
- ii. Kruskal-Wallis Test was conducted to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in similarity and AI scores across different academic disciplines.
- iii. Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was computed to test the strength and direction of the relationship between the similarity index and AI-generated content score.

Content analysis was also performed on selected examples of AIgiarism to identify common patterns of misuse and the specific sections of the paper most vulnerable to AI content generation.

Ethical Considerations

All data were handled in accordance with ethical research standards. Authors' identities were anonymised to ensure confidentiality, and all identifying information was removed from the

dataset. The study obtained approval from the organisers of the conference to use submitted materials for research purposes. The findings are intended solely for research purposes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 represents the data obtained on plagiarism scores for the publications across different academic disciplines. The majority of papers across all disciplines (51.35%) fall into the "Below 20%" similarity score category. Only a small proportion (18.92%) has similarity scores "Above 40%," The discipline with the lowest indices is computing where the majority, (80%) of the papers in the discipline show less than 20% similarity score.

Table 1: Plagiarism Index of Scientific Papers

Disciplines	Below 20	20-40	Above 40	Total
Environmental Science	4 (66.67%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	6 (100%)
Materials science and Engineering	2 (66.67%)	-	1 (33.3%)	3 (100%)
Computing	4 (80%)		1 (20%)	5 (100%)
Nutrition	3 (60%)	2 (40%)		5 (100%)
Biochemistry	2 (33.33%)	3 (50%)	1 (16.67%)	6 (100%)
Biotechnology and Microbiology	2 (33.33%)	4 (66.67%)	-	6 (100%)
Agriculture	2 (50%)	1 (25%)	1 (25%)	4 (100%)
Health	-	-	2 (100%)	2 (100%)
Total	19 (51.35%)	11 (29.73%)	7 (18.92%)	37 (100%)

About half of the papers (51.35%) across all academic disciplines exhibited low similarity scores (below 20%), indicating a fairly responsible adherence to academic integrity. However, the existence of some subtle forms of plagiarism that may not be easy detectable through plagiarism detection tools should be noted, for example, branded plagiarism and commission plagiarism (Mireku, Dzamesi & Bervell, 2024). Also, though low plagiarism papers are in a slight majority, for a serious issue like academic integrity, this percentage of papers that appear to have low levels of plagiarism is still not impressive. Computing papers demonstrate the lowest similarity indices among all disciplines. Some reasons for the low indices could be the unique nature of the subject area with its novel algorithmic development or coding/programming nature, compared to disciplines that rely more heavily on extensive literature reviews and theoretical discussions. Thus, computing research would naturally lead to less textual overlap with existing literature. Also, self efficacy, technical skills and competencies of computing researchers could contribute to higher proficiency in manipulating text to reduce similarity rates.

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Research Question 2: Which sections of research papers are most frequently affected by plagiarism?

Table 2 shows the distribution of scientific papers with AI scores within the range of (0%, below 20, 20-40 and above 40) across various scientific disciplines. From Table 2, it can be observed that the disciplines that fall into the 0% compliance category constitute 43.24% of the total number of papers, while the those "Above 40" represent 13.51%. The publications reflect mostly low AI usage.

Table 2: AI scores of scientific papers

Disciplines	0%	Below 20	20-40	Above 40	Total
Environmental Science	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	6 (100%)
Material Science and Engineering		1 (33.3%)		2 (66.6%)	3 (100%)
Computing	2 (40.0%)	1(20.0%)	1 (20.0%)	1(20.0%)	5 (100%)
Nutrition	3 (60%)	1 (20.0%)	1 (20.0%)		5 (100%)
Biochemistry	2 (33.3%)	3 (50.0%)	-	1(16.7%)	6 (100%)
Biotechnology and Microbiology	4 (66.6%)	1 (16.7%)	1(16.7%)	-	6 (100%)
Agriculture	1 (25.0%)	2 (50.0%)	1 (25.5%)		4 (100%)
Health	2 (100%)				2 (100%)
Total	16 (43.24%)	11 (29.73%)	5 (13.51%)	5 (13.51%)	37 (100%)

Regarding AI-generated research, the distribution of AI scores in scientific papers indicates a predominantly low usage of AI tools in their creation. Most of the papers, 43.24%, fall into the 0% category, which suggests no detectable AI use. This overall trend towards low AI usage could be as a result of researchers knowledge and experience, as they would know the essence of maintaining academic integrity to avoid rejection of their submissions. This also aligns with the findings of Bin-Nashwan et al. (2023) which found that academic integrity guides responsible AI use, mitigating negative motives like peer pressure while enhancing positive, ethical outcomes. Also, the specialised nature of scientific writing, which often requires technical language and unique experimental details with specific interpretations, might not predispose the papers to AIgiarism.

Research Question 1: What are the common types of plagiarism observed in the corpus of papers?

Eighteen papers had over 20% plagiarism as presented in Table 3. The Table reflects the plagiarism typologies observed in these papers. The results show that "mosaic and missing quotations" (55.5%) is the most prevalent type of plagiarism, followed by "verbatim and missing

quotations", which represents the next largest category at 16.6%. Other forms of plagiarism are less common.

Table 3: Commonest types of Plagiarism

Type of Plagiarism	Frequency	Percentage
Verbatim	1	5.5%
Verbatim copying and self plagiarism	1	5.5%
Verbatim and missing quotations	3	16.6%
Mosaic plagiarism	1	5.5%
Mosaic and missing quotations	10	55.5%
Self-plagiarism	1	5.5%
Mixed (Aigiarism, verbatim, mosaic and missing quotation, self-plagiarism)	1	5.5%
	18	100%

* For papers with plagiarism above 20

The results presented in Table 3 show that mosaic and missing quotations (53.0%) is the predominant form of plagiarism in the analysed papers. According to De Amicis (2023), “mosaic plagiarism pulls from multiple-authored sources without proper attribution, and misrepresents the originality of a student’s submission” and is also referred to as patchwork plagiarism. This prevalence suggests that authors find information from various sources and integrate them without proper attributions. This might suggest deliberate acts of plagiarism possibly to save time or due to peer pressure (De Amicis, 2023). The next most common type of plagiarism, verbatim and missing quotations (16.6%), indicates direct copying without proper citation and reflects poor paraphrasing skills, or a deliberate attempt to disguise unoriginal content. The lower occurrence of other plagiarism types like pure verbatim or self-plagiarism suggests that while these are present, the mosaic or patchwork is the most aggressive form (Konstantinidis, Theodosiadou & Pappos, 2013).

Research Question 2: Which sections of research papers are most frequently affected by Plagiarism?

Widespread	10	36%
Based on 10 papers with selective Plagiarism		
Abstract	3	11%
Introduction/Background/Literature Review	7	25%
Materials and Methods	3	11%

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Results	3	11%
Discussion/Conclusion/Recommendation	2	7%

The prevalence and distribution of plagiarism within the analysed papers reveal a significant pattern as shown in Table 4. Out of 28 papers with high similarity index (over 20% SI), 36% of the papers contained plagiarised content across nearly all sections, 25% showed plagiarism concentrated in the Introduction/ Background or Literature Review. Such sections could have a high amount of plagiarism because they involve the integration of existing scholarly work synthesised into one section. The Methodology, Results, Conclusion and Recommendation sections could indicate lower levels of plagiarism because they are supposed to be unique or original since they are context-dependent and developed from the researcher's empirical findings and critical interpretation (Tobin, 2014).

Research Question 3: Which sections of research papers are most frequently AI-generation?

Table 5 shows which sections of research papers were most frequently AI-generated content, based on 10 papers with AI scores of 20 and above. The data reveals that AI-generated content most frequently affects the "Introduction/Background" section, a trend evident in all 10 examined papers (100%). The "Conclusion/Recommendation" section is the next most affected, as the trend is observed in 7 out of 10 papers (70%). Other sections show varying degrees of AI content. The "Literature Review" (20%) and "Discussion" (20%) and "Title" (10%) sections were the least affected.

Table 5: Sections of research papers most frequently affected by AI-generated content

Sections of Research Paper	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Title									<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		1
Abstract	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		5
Introduction/Background	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10									
Literature Review		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						2
Materials and Methods		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6
Results		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				5
Discussion					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2
Conclusion/Recommendation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			7				

*Only 10 papers qualified for checking because they have AI scores from 20 and above.

AI might be used to summarize findings. This is likely due to the structured and predictable elements of these sections. The moderate presence of AI content in "Materials and Methods" and Abstract sections might reflect the use of AI for drafting technical descriptions or concise summaries.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁): There is no significant difference in similarity scores among papers from different scientific disciplines.

Table 6 is a summary of the Kruskal-Wallis Test conducted to test the null hypothesis 1: (H₀₁) which stated that there is no significant difference in similarity scores among papers from different scientific disciplines. The results yielded a test statistic of $H(7) = 8.964$ with a p-value of 0.255. Since this p-value is greater than the chosen significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis was not rejected. This finding indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in similarity scores among the different subject areas. Any observed variations are likely due to random chance rather than a true disciplinary difference.

Table 6: Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis H Test Summary on Similarity scores across Scientific Disciplines

Total N	37
Test Statistic	8.964 ^{a,b}
Degree Of Freedom	7
Asymptotic Sig.(2-sided test)	.255

- a. The test statistic is adjusted for ties.
- b. Multiple comparisons are not performed because the overall test does not show significant differences across samples.

Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂): There is no significant difference in AI-generated content scores across academic disciplines

Based on the result obtained after the Kruskal-Wallis H Test to confirm differences in AI scores across disciplines (Hypothesis 2) involving 37 papers (Total N = 37) and compared across 8 distinct subject areas (Degree of Freedom = 7). The calculated test statistic, adjusted for ties was 10.485. The Asymptotic Significance (2-sided test) value obtained was 0.163, and is greater than the chosen significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), thus the null hypothesis is accepted since $0.163 > 0.05$. This means that there is no statistically significant difference in AI-generated content scores among the different subject areas. This evidence suggests that any observed variations in AI scores among subject areas are likely due to chance among the different subject areas rather than a true difference.

The hypothesis testing (H₀₁ and H₀₂) aimed at exploring the differences in plagiarism and Aigiariism practices across various disciplines and also to understand the nature of the relationship between plagiarism and Aigiariism, or massive generation of research content through AI generation tools. The findings show that there is no significant difference across the

defined disciplines in their practice of plagiarism or AIgiarism. Eshet (2025) explores these disciplinary dynamics. The study reveals discipline-based differences in plagiarism, with STEM students being more prone to academic dishonesty than those in the humanities or social sciences. However, during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, plagiarism in the humanities rose significantly and thereafter aligned with STEM's rates. Thus, there might be a difference in the studies covered if other disciplines in humanities and social science which use radically different methods and registers from the science and technology were used. Thus, the similarity in academic writing and methodological conventions might have provided a consistent baseline across the various subject areas (science and technology).

Table 7: Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis H Test Summary on differences in AI scores across disciplines:

Total N	37
Test Statistic	10.485 ^{a,b}
Degree of Freedom	7
Asymptotic Sig.(2-sided test)	.163

a. The test statistic is adjusted for ties.

b Multiple comparisons are not performed because the overall test does not show significant differences across samples.

Hypothesis 3 (H₀₃): There is no correlation between similarity scores and AI-generated content scores in the submitted papers.

A Spearman's rho correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between similarity scores and AI-generated content scores, where a total of 37 data pairs were analysed. The results indicated a correlation coefficient (r) = -0.357 , which was statistically significant (p = 0.030). The results of the correlation analysis indicate a statistically significant negative correlation between similarity scores and AI-generated content scores. The observed Spearman's rho of -0.357 suggests a moderate inverse relationship, meaning that as the proportion of AI-generated content in a paper increases, the similarity score tends to decrease. Also, papers with higher similarity scores tend to exhibit lower AI-generated content scores. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected – there is a negative correlation between the two variables.

Table 8: Spearman's rho correlation analysis on relationship between similarity scores and AI-generated content scores

Correlations			Similarity Score	AI Score
Spearman's rho	similarity score	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.357*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.030
		N	37	37
	AI score	Correlation Coefficient	-.357*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.030	.
		N	37	37

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The negative correlation between the similarity scores and AI-generated content could be possible because AI models, when generating text, synthesize information in new ways that reduce direct matches to existing sources. Also, researchers who use of the AI tools do so to avoid high similarity scores by rephrasing or generating “original” content through AI. Thus, it is highly probable that AI-based content and traditional plagiarism are inversely related. The implications are that AI-generated content might inadvertently, or intentionally, contribute to lower similarity scores. This is supported by Zhou et al. (2025) who report the prevalence yet subtle nature of paraphrased plagiarism. This poses a complex challenge for detection tools that traditionally rely on high similarity as an of indicator plagiarism.

CONCLUSION

Academic integrity has become important in current times because of the availability of many tools that make research easy (Merku, Dzamesi & Bervell, 2024) and thus promote “unoriginal” content and academic misconduct. This study on AIgiarism and plagiarism seeks to observe the current trends in scientific writing to provide evidence-based suggestions and recommendations for academics, researchers, reviewers, supervisors, developers of academic tools and students. From the findings, many papers (over 50%) exhibited low similarity scores (below 20%). This reflects a general adherence to academic integrity, however the percentage of papers that fell above 20% is also significantly high. This is a pointer to the need to sustain interventions towards academic integrity. Though papers in computing were shown to be least susceptible to plagiarism, factors inherent in the discipline could have contributed to the difference.

The prevalence of mosaic plagiarism, missing quotations, and verbatim plagiarism indicates the possibility of deliberate rather than unintentional plagiarism. Most of the papers had the entire or multiple sections of the papers affected by plagiarism. This is critical, especially if important sections such as the abstract, methods and materials and results are also involved. The level of AI

usage is also a cause for concern. Of the papers with high AI scores, all (100%) had AI-generated content in the introduction, and 70% had it in the conclusions and recommendations. Concerning the association between the AI status and the plagiarism, an inverse relationship was observed: papers with high AI content tended to have low plagiarism scores, and vice versa. This suggests that AI use and traditional plagiarism may be alternative strategies for producing unoriginal content. The researchers were either plagiarising or depending heavily on AI, neither of which is an acceptable practice in view of academic integrity. This provides an emerging challenge for plagiarism detection tools due to paraphrasing plagiarism, which may result from unmoderated generation of content from AI. In effect, to sustain the ethos of honesty, trust, fairness, respect, and responsibility, researchers need to understand the ethical use of sourced information.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are suggested:

- i. There is need for greater emphasis on academic integrity through education in the form of workshops and training sessions specifically directed at proper citation, paraphrasing, and ethical AI tool use. Focused training based on the findings from studies such as this will likely yield better results.
- ii. Institutional policies should be strengthened through documentation and implementation within academic and research communities to support ethical research practices and academic integrity.
- iii. Methods of plagiarism detection might need re-engineering as more sophisticated forms of plagiarism are emerging because of advances in generative AI.
- iv. Reviewers and editors should undergo advanced training to recognize patterns indicative of AI-generated content, even when similarity scores are low.
- v. Clear guidelines should be established for the ethical use of AI tools in academic writing. Researchers should be able to draw the line between acceptable assistance versus unacknowledged generation of core content or a replacement for original thought and critical analysis. Also, transparency should be encouraged, particularly on the role of AI in the research work through disclosure statements, to sustain the ethos of academic integrity.
- vi. Future research could emphasize the concept of AIgjarism and also widen the scope of the study to include the humanities and social sciences.
- vii. Longitudinal studies could be attempted to track trends over time to observe the evolving impact of AI on academic writing and integrity.

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